

RE-ADJUSTool

REFlecting on & ADVancing Justice
in Urban food STRategies

YOUR TURN!
rotating facilitator

NOW YOU'RE TALKING!
reflexive question cards

Would you like to discuss with others how social added value is or can be created in the food system of your city?

With the RE-ADJUSTool you can jointly unpack and tackle the theme of social justice in urban food policies and initiatives in an accessible and co-creative way!

ALL CARDS ON THE TABLE!
peeking allowed

ORGANISE YOUR THOUGHTS!
messy notes & structured to-do's

Cite as: Smaal, S.A.L. & Rogge, E. (2021). RE-ADJUSTool: REflecting on and ADvancing Justice in Urban food STRategies. H2020 MSCA-ITN 'RECOMS'.

Design by: Roos Gellynck & Daphné Roels (OMGEVING)

✉ : READJUSTool@gmail.com & elke.rogge@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

duration: ±3.5 hours
3 sessions: ±1-1.5 hours

4-8 players

ILVO
Flanders Research Institute for
Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 765389.

EXAMPLE PLAYING BOARD

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Print this document on A3 or A4 paper (single-sided, if possible on thick paper). Also download the instructions and R&C sheet and print these on A4 paper (double-sided).
- Cut out the cards and the playing board elements and place them on the table as explained in the instructions and illustrated in the example.
- Download the discussion and personal notes sheets and print as many as you need (see also instructions) on A4 paper or use your own note material.
- Optional: Make a folder out of the first two sheets in this document using tape in order to keep the game components safe before and after use. You can also use a box or envelope.

USTool

EDISTRIBUTION

1. ECONOMIC R

RE-ADJ

RE-ADJ

2. CULTURAL

RECOGNITION

USTool

REPRESENTATION

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* ECONOMIC REDISTRIBUTION *
INFRASTRUCTURE & TOOLS

Access to the transportation, equipment and logistics needed for producing, purchasing and trading food.

* CULTURAL RECOGNITION *
APPRECIATION & FULFILMENT

Access to opportunities to gain respect, enjoyment and satisfaction out of food-related labour.

* CULTURAL RECOGNITION *
SUSTAINABILITY & BIODIVERSITY

Access to opportunities to acknowledge non-human life and future generations through food choices.

* ECONOMIC REDISTRIBUTION *
FOOD & HEALTH

Access to adequate, safe and nutritious diets.

* ECONOMIC REDISTRIBUTION *
SPACE & LAND

Access to sites to grow, produce, prepare or share food.

* CULTURAL RECOGNITION *
COHESION & ENCOUNTERS

Access to opportunities to meet and connect with others through food-related activities.

* CULTURAL RECOGNITION *
KNOWLEDGE & SKILLS

Access to opportunities to practice, share and develop food-related expertise.

* ECONOMIC REDISTRIBUTION *
EMPLOYMENT & REMUNERATION

Access to fair and decent pay for food-related labour and products.

* POLITICAL REPRESENTATION *
INFORMATION & TRANSPARENCY

Access to structures that provide detailed and reliable information on food systems.

* EVALUATION *

question 3
RE-ADJUSTool assessment

Based on our conversations so far, on a scale from 0 to 3, to what extent are each of these four types of resources being addressed in our current food policy documents and efforts?

Visualise your collective scores in the central figure. Start with the aspect that has received the least attention.

economic redistribution

* EVALUATION *

question 1
policy target groups

- For whom is the city trying to improve access to these types of resources, and why?
- What concrete action steps have been taken to reach vulnerable and disadvantaged groups and communities?

economic redistribution

* POLITICAL REPRESENTATION *
VOICE & PARTICIPATION

Access to structures that give citizens and organisations a say in decision-making on food issues.

* POLITICAL REPRESENTATION *
PLATFORMS & SUPPORT

Access to structures that assist, guide and stimulate citizens and organisations in the field of food.

* BRAINSTORM *

question 1
collaborative action

- What would be effective ways to improve access to these types of resources in our city?
- How can we create a broad base of support for these ideas?

economic redistribution

* EVALUATION *

question 2
facilitative support

- What food initiatives in our city are trying to improve access to these types of resources from the ground up?
- In what ways are these initiatives being supported? How can this support be improved?

economic redistribution

* POLITICAL REPRESENTATION *
LAW & REGULATIONS

Access to structures that establish the legal frameworks for citizens and organisations within the food system.

* EVALUATION *

question 1
policy target groups

- For whom is the city trying to improve access to these types of opportunities, and why?
- What concrete action steps have been taken to reach vulnerable and disadvantaged groups and communities?

cultural recognition

* EVALUATION *

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- What food initiatives in our city are trying to improve access to these types of structures from the ground up?
- In what ways are these initiatives being supported? How can this support be improved?

political representation

* BRAINSTORM *

question 2
citizen empowerment

- Who tend to lack access to these types of resources? Why?
- How can the municipality enable these groups to take part in the food system with dignity?

economic redistribution

* BRAINSTORM *

question 3
RE-ADJUSTool prioritisation

Based on our conversations so far, on a scale from 0 to 3, how much importance should be attributed to each of these four types of resources in our city's future food policy documents and efforts?

Visualise your collective scores in the central figure. Start with the aspect that most urgently needs to be addressed.

economic redistribution

* EVALUATION *

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